

Filename: Nextera DNA library 13_25.D5000

Gel Images

Samples
patient_site_day-of-sampling

- 13 : 2_ETA_3
- 14 : 2_ETA_6
- 15 : 2_BAL_9
- 16 : 5_ETA_3
- 17 : 5_ETA_9
- 18 : 5_ETA_15
- 19 : 8_ETA_4
- 20 : 8_ETA_9
- 21 : 8_ETA_12
- 22 : 1_ETA_6
- 23 : 1_ETA_9
- 24 : 1_BAL_VAP
- 25 : TN2

Default image (Contrast 50%), Image is Scaled to Sample, Image is Scaled to view larger Molecular Weight range

Sample Info

Well	Conc. [ng/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
A1	49.3	Ladder		Ladder
B1	6.04	13n		
C1	9.02	14n		
D1	22.9	15n		
E1	29.2	16n		
F1	2.84	17n		
G1	21.9	18n		
H1	3.24	19n		
A2	25.1	20n		
B2	26.5	21n		
C2	15.8	22n		
D2	7.98	23n		
E2	3.68	24n		
F2	0.186	25n		

A1: Ladder

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [ng/μl]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
A1	49.3	Ladder		Ladder

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [ng/μl]	Assigned Conc. [ng/μl]	Peak Molarity [nmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	7.11	-	729	-		Lower Marker
100	5.06	-	77.8	10.25		
250	5.54	-	34.1	11.23		
400	5.68	-	21.8	11.51		
600	5.86	-	15.0	11.87		
1000	5.89	-	9.06	11.93		
1500	5.72	-	5.86	11.59		
2500	5.67	-	3.49	11.50		
3500	5.35	-	2.35	10.85		
5000	4.57	-	1.41	9.26		
10000	3.25	3.25	0.500	-		Upper Marker

B1: 13n**Sample Table**

Well	Conc. [ng/μl]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
B1	6.04	13n		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [ng/μl]	Assigned Conc. [ng/μl]	Peak Molarity [nmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	8.57	-	879	-		Lower Marker
37	3.33	-	138	55.11		
793	1.94	-	3.77	32.16		
4674	0.769	-	0.253	12.73		
10000	3.25	3.25	0.500	-		Upper Marker

C1: 14n

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [ng/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
C1	9.02	14n		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [ng/ul]	Assigned Conc. [ng/ul]	Peak Molarity [nmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	8.02	-	822	-		Lower Marker
31	3.50	-	177	38.83		
263	5.06	-	29.6	56.09		
4389	0.459	-	0.161	5.08		
10000	3.25	3.25	0.500	-		Upper Marker

D1: 15n

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [ng/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
D1	22.9	15n		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [ng/ul]	Assigned Conc. [ng/ul]	Peak Molarity [nmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	10.8	-	1110	-		Lower Marker
192	22.5	-	180	98.41		
4100	0.364	-	0.137	1.59		
10000	3.25	3.25	0.500	-		Upper Marker

E1: 16n**Sample Table**

Well	Conc. [ng/μl]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
E1	29.2	16n		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [ng/μl]	Assigned Conc. [ng/μl]	Peak Molarity [nmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	8.41	-	863	-		Lower Marker
34	4.61	-	207	15.78		
2919	24.3	-	12.8	82.98		
4045	0.361	-	0.137	1.24		
10000	3.25	3.25	0.500	-		Upper Marker

F1: 17n

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [ng/μl]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
F1	2.84	17n		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [ng/μl]	Assigned Conc. [ng/μl]	Peak Molarity [nmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	8.88	-	911	-		Lower Marker
34	2.84	-	127	100.00		
10000	3.25	3.25	0.500	-		Upper Marker

G1: 18n

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [ng/μl]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
G1	21.9	18n		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [ng/μl]	Assigned Conc. [ng/μl]	Peak Molarity [nmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	8.48	-	870	-		Lower Marker
200	21.9	-	169	100.00		
10000	3.25	3.25	0.500	-		Upper Marker

H1: 19n

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [ng/μl]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
H1	3.24	19n		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [ng/μl]	Assigned Conc. [ng/μl]	Peak Molarity [nmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	8.38	-	860	-		Lower Marker
38	3.24	-	132	100.00		
10000	3.25	3.25	0.500	-		Upper Marker

A2: 20n

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [ng/μl]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
A2	25.1	20n		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [ng/μl]	Assigned Conc. [ng/μl]	Peak Molarity [nmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	8.02	-	823	-		Lower Marker
31	2.26	-	112	8.98		
189	22.9	-	186	91.02		
10000	3.25	3.25	0.500	-		Upper Marker

B2: 21n

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [ng/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
B2	26.5	21n		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [ng/ul]	Assigned Conc. [ng/ul]	Peak Molarity [nmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	8.45	-	867	-		Lower Marker
208	26.5	-	196	100.00		
10000	3.25	3.25	0.500	-		Upper Marker

C2: 22n

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [ng/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
C2	15.8	22n		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [ng/ul]	Assigned Conc. [ng/ul]	Peak Molarity [nmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	7.59	-	779	-		Lower Marker
26	3.88	-	228	24.60		
226	11.9	-	80.9	75.40		
10000	3.25	3.25	0.500	-		Upper Marker

D2: 23n

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [ng/μl]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
D2	7.98	23n		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [ng/μl]	Assigned Conc. [ng/μl]	Peak Molarity [nmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	7.33	-	752	-		Lower Marker
31	2.83	-	142	35.45		
292	1.65	-	8.69	20.71		
460	1.79	-	5.99	22.46		
794	1.19	-	2.30	14.89		
4171	0.518	-	0.191	6.49		
10000	3.25	3.25	0.500	-		Upper Marker

E2: 24n

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [ng/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
E2	3.68	24n		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [ng/ul]	Assigned Conc. [ng/ul]	Peak Molarity [nmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	9.04	-	927	-		Lower Marker
35	3.68	-	161	100.00		
10000	3.25	3.25	0.500	-		Upper Marker

F2: 25n

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [ng/μl]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
F2	0.186	25n		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [ng/μl]	Assigned Conc. [ng/μl]	Peak Molarity [nmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	9.24	-	948	-		Lower Marker
3875	0.186	-	0.0740	100.00		
10000	3.25	3.25	0.500	-		Upper Marker